

COMPUTATIONAL MODELING OF LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT RESPONSE OF WOVEN CARBON LAMINATES IN ARCTIC CONDITIONS

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1 General Introduction

Ice melting in the Arctic has led to the creation of two new passages (Northwest and Northeast), which can become viable transportation routes in the future [1]. This has resulted in a rise in demand and interest in Arctic exploration, which has brought new challenges regarding the mechanical behavior of lightweight composites used in offshore structures. Composites are typically preferred for ship structures due to their lightweight, enhanced performance and affordability. However, these materials typically experience drastic changes and degradation in their macro-and-microstructures when exposed to seawater and cold temperatures in-service. Therefore, it is critical to have a detailed comprehension of the mechanical behavior and failure mechanisms of layered composites at low-temperatures [2]. Despite the several advantages of layered fiber reinforced composites (FRPs), a major drawback is their low resistance to impact damage. The objective of this research is to develop a computational model within the finite element method (FEA) framework that is able to predict damage and failure mechanisms such as delamination, matrix cracking and fiber fracture of FRPs during a low-velocity impact event at room temperature (25 °C) and arctic temperatures (-50 °C).

2 Methods

2.1 Impact tests

An impact test was performed in a drop tower impact system according to the ASTM D7136, where a rectangular laminate of 150 mm length x 100 mm width with a 4 mm thickness was impacted by a hemispherical striker at its center in the out-of-plane direction with a given kinetic energy. The kinetic energy was calculated based on the striker mass and velocity (impact velocity) using equation (1).

$$E_k = \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = mgh \quad (1)$$

E_k is the impact or kinetic energy, m is the mass of the striker, v is the impact velocity, h is the height of the striker measured from the surface of a sample in the impact drop tower, and g is the gravitational acceleration.

2.1 Impact simulations

A laminate with 16 layers of plain weave carbon fiber layers within FEM using a commercially available software (ABAQUS) was modeled. The model consisted of 31 layers in total: 16 layers of homogenized plain weave carbon fabric and 15 layers of matrix material (vinyl ester resin). The boundary conditions of the model were based on the fixture corresponding to a CEAST 9340 Drop Tower Impact System, which clamps the specimen with 0.2 MPa between two metal fixtures with a test area of 46 cm², as shown in Figure 1a. For the computational model, only the region of the laminate enclosed within the metal fixture was considered, as this was the main region influenced during low-velocity impact loading, as shown in Figure 1b.

2.2 Damage model

To simulate the damage during an impact event, two distinct formulations were used: i) a damage model to address the matrix and fiber damage at the lamina level and II) a cohesive damage model to account for delamination between lamina.

2.2.1 Lamina damage model

Each layer of woven carbon fiber was modeled as a homogenized lamina with orthotropic properties. Each layer had a thickness of 0.229 mm and was meshed with continuum shell elements (SC8R in ABAQUS). The damage model required the elastic properties and strength of the lamina. The damage

onset was dictated by Hashin’s damage criterion. For the damage propagation, four components of the fracture toughness were required. Properties of woven carbon fiber reinforced in vinyl ester resin are summarized in Table 1.

2.1.2 Interlaminar region (matrix)

The resin rich regions were simulated using cohesive zone elements. The thickness of each layer of matrix was 0.05 mm. Cohesive zone modeling was used for the matrix, which was meshed with cohesive elements (COHD3 in ABAQUS). The cohesive zone modeling required the elastic properties of the matrix, the interface strengths for pure mode I and shear modes (II and III), and the interface fracture toughness for pure mode I and shear modes (II and III) [3]. The vinyl ester resin properties are summarized in Table 2.

2.1.1 Striker

The hemispherical striker was modeled as a rigid body, which was meshed with discrete rigid elements (R3D4 in ABAQUS). It had a diameter of $\phi=12.7$ mm and a mass of $m=3$ kg. Its motion was governed by a single reference point. Surface-to-surface contact between the striker and the impacted laminate surface was added using the contact algorithm.

3 Results and conclusion

The experimental and simulated impact contact force responses corresponding to an impact energy of 25 J at room temperature is shown in Figure 2. The numerical simulation does not exactly replicate the experimental tests; however, the overall trend of the curve between the experimental test and the simulation is comparable.

4 Future Work

- Further investigation will be pursued to match the numerical simulation with the experimental result.
- Temperature will be added to the simulation to account for the damage when the laminate is exposed to -50 °C.

5 Figures and Tables

Fig 1. a) Impact fixture schematic. b) Modeling domain.

Fig 2. Comparison between numerical and experimental force-time responses for 25 J at 25 °C.

Density (tonne/mm ³)	$\rho=2 \times 10^{-9}$		
Elastic properties (MPa)	$E_1=E_2=37000$	$E_3=4720$	$\nu_{12}=0.3 \quad \nu_{13}=\nu_{23}=0.4$
Lamina strength (MPa)	$G_{12}=5200$	$G_{13}=G_{23}=5200$	
Fracture toughness (N/mm)	$X^T=Y^T=1707$	$X^C=Y^C=1031$	$S^L=S^T=85.875$
	Longitudinal and transverse tensile= 60		Longitudinal and transverse compressive=80

Table 1. Plain weave woven carbon laminate properties

Density (tonne/mm ³)	$\rho=6.15 \times 10^{-11}$		
Elastic properties (MPa)	$E=3400$	$G=1300$	$\nu=0.3$
Interface strength (MPa)	Normal mode=53.78	1st and 2nd direction=86.88	
Fracture toughness (N/mm)	Normal mode=1.4	Shear mode (1st and 2nd direction)=0.7	

Table 2. Interlaminar region properties (vinyl ester)

References

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